

Key Points:

- A predictive framework based on an idea of scale separation is proposed for the mean velocity of the flow passing through an array of cylinders
- The framework is versatile, being applicable for a wide range of practically meaningful cylinder arrangements, array shapes and array flow blockages
- High-fidelity, three-dimensional direct numerical simulations are employed to investigate flow through the array of cylinders and validate the new predictive framework

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Citation:

He, F., Draper, S., Ghisalberti, M., An, H., & Branson, P. (2024). Predicting mean flow through an array of cylinders. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 51, e2024GL110164. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL110164>

Received 21 MAY 2024

Accepted 12 JUN 2024

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Abstract The present paper develops a new predictive framework in which the flow around the array (array-scale) and the flow around individual cylinders (element-scale) are modeled separately using actuator disc theory and empirical drag models respectively, and then coupled through the net drag force. Applying this framework only requires knowledge of the array geometry and incident flow. This framework is validated using high-fidelity direct numerical simulations for arrays of between 7 and 109 cylinders having different arrangements (staggered, concentric, random) and bounding shapes (circular, square) in both two- and three-dimensional flows. In general, the framework outperforms existing models which require calibration and are only valid for part of the practical parameter space. The demonstrated scale separation suggests different combinations of element-scale and array-scale models/theories may be used for other arrangements of bluff bodies.

Plain Language Summary The temporally and spatially averaged velocity, or mean flow, within an array of cylinders is important for many practical applications including, for example, estimating the rates of sediment transport and nutrient uptake within a patch of aquatic vegetation, the hydrodynamic forces on offshore structures, and the efficiency of power generation with a turbine farm. However, a general predictive tool for mean flow is currently lacking. To develop this predictive capacity, this study uses the idea of scale separation to integrate models from different research fields, including the actuator disc theory originally developed for design of turbines and propellers, and element-scale drag models initially proposed for aquatic vegetated flows, to develop a unifying, predictive, analytical framework to estimate the mean flow. The framework is validated using high-fidelity direct numerical simulations, for arrays with different arrangements (staggered, concentric, random) and shapes (square, circular). With only knowledge of the array geometry and incident flow, the framework predicts the mean flow exceptionally well across the full range of practical flow conditions. This leads to a step-change in our ability to predict the fraction of incoming flow passing through a porous array, hydrodynamic load on offshore structures, and sediment flux within aquatic vegetation systems when combined with bed load transport models. We believe this framework will be an important guide for coastal and riverine restoration projects using aquatic vegetation and the design of offshore structures and turbine farms.

1. Introduction

Flows through an array of elements occur ubiquitously in natural and engineered systems, such as flows through patches of aquatic vegetation (e.g., saltmarshes, reeds), groups of bridge piers, pile foundations, offshore jacket structures, and arrays of turbines. The spatially and temporally averaged bulk velocity within an array, here termed the “mean flow,” controls many key processes in the array. For example, the mean flow influences rates of sediment transport (Zong & Nepf, 2012) and nutrient uptake (Koch et al., 2007) in a vegetation patch and the length of the steady wake region into which the patch preferentially propagates (Chen et al., 2012). The mean flow also controls the efficiency of power generation with a turbine farm (Garrett & Cummins, 2013) and hydrodynamic loads on offshore structures (Taylor, 1991). These practical applications highlight the importance of having predictive capacity of mean flow.

An array of emergent cylinders (Figure 1a) is a good first approximation for many of these practical systems (Nicolle & Eames, 2011). When flow interacts with this array, a portion will pass through the array, whilst the remainder will be diverted around it (Figure 1b). The mean flow through the array is influenced by the dimensionless flow blockage parameter Γ_D (Chang & Constantinescu, 2015), which represents the ratio between the drag and advection terms in the streamwise momentum equation describing flow through the array (Chang & Constantinescu, 2015) and is defined as

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Figure 1. (a) Side view and (b) plan view of an array of emergent cylinders in three-dimensional flow; (c) flow through a porous disc; (d) close-up view of element-scale wake structure associated with individual cylinders, similar to that within an infinite arrangement of cylinders (hollow circles).

$$\Gamma_D = \frac{C_d a D}{(1 - \phi)}, \quad (1)$$

where $a = nd$ is the total frontal area of cylinders per unit volume of the array (with n the number of cylinders per unit area and d the element diameter), D is the array diameter, $\phi (= (\pi/4)nd^2)$ is the solid volume fraction of the array, and C_d is expressed as

$$C_d = \frac{F_{total}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho N dh (\langle \bar{u} \rangle / (1 - \phi))^2}, \quad (2)$$

in which F_{total} is the total drag force acting on the array, ρ is the fluid density, N is the total number of cylinders in the array, and h is the water depth. The mean streamwise flow $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ is obtained by taking averages of the streamwise velocity over the volume of the array (denoted by the angled brackets), and then over a period of time that is much longer compared with the time scale of flow motions at both the element scale and the array scale (denoted by an over-bar). With increasing Γ_D , the array produces a larger flow resistance to reduce the mean flow through the array.

The flow blockage parameter for practical systems spans a wide range of values $O(0.1 - 100)$ (e.g., Rominger & Nepf, 2011; Tanino & Nepf, 2008). Within this range, systems can have different arrangements of elements and different array shapes. For instance, individual shoots are randomly distributed within a circular vegetation patch (Zong & Nepf, 2012), whilst mangroves and seagrasses are often organized in a staggered pattern within a square or circular region in restoration programs (He, 2023; van Katwijk et al., 2016). At present, however, there is no

general closed-form solution to predict the mean flow for these systems which spans the full practical range of Γ_D . An existing model, requiring calibration, has been proposed to predict the velocity behind the array for high flow blockage (Zong & Nepf, 2012), and for low flow blockage (Creed et al., 2017), however, neither model shows good agreement with measurements outside of these limited ranges of Γ_D .

To develop a more comprehensive empirical model, this paper hypothesizes that the flow field can be modeled by considering the external (array-scale) and internal (element-scale) flows separately, using separate array-scale and element-scale theories/models, respectively. These scales are then coupled by ensuring the bulk force influencing the array scale is equal to the net drag experienced by the local elements due to the mean flow through the array.

At the array-scale, “actuator disc” theory is adopted, given that it has been used to relate the bulk flow field to the thrust produced by turbines and propellers (Taylor, 1944; van Kuik, 2004). In this theory (Garrett & Cummins, 2007) a permeable actuator disc with assumed negligible thickness is used to represent the obstruction in a channel (Figure 1c) and the theory establishes a relationship between the bulk drag on the disc (expressed by Γ_D) and the bulk flow through it ($\langle \bar{u} \rangle$) without resolving the internal flow within the obstruction. It is normally assumed that the disc has a sufficiently small resistance (i.e., low Γ_D) so that the time-averaged flow field can be represented as a smoothly expanding stream tube (blue dashed lines in Figure 1c) that encompasses the disc. Whilst actuator disc theory has been conventionally applied to design turbines and propellers, this study seeks to determine the applicability of actuator disc theory to model an array of vertical cylinders (rather than a number of blades).

In comparison to the array-scale problem, there is a range of models that can be adopted to describe the element-scale drag for arrangements of cylinders representative of the internal structure of the array (Figure 1d). For instance, there is an empirical model of flow through an infinitely wide, random arrangement of cylinders, which quantifies the element drag coefficient as a function of ϕ and Reynolds number $Re = \langle \bar{u} \rangle d / ((1 - \phi)\nu)$, where ν is the kinematic viscosity) (Tanino & Nepf, 2008). For simplicity, the element drag coefficient has also sometimes been modeled using $C_d = 1$ (Zong & Nepf, 2012), which is close to that for an isolated cylinder when $Re > O(100)$ (Tanino & Nepf, 2008).

Since C_d (in Γ_D) and $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ (in Re) are interdependent and both are unknown a priori, neither the array-scale nor element-scale models/theories independently provide a closed-form solution to this problem. However, combining both models through these quantities leads to a single modeling framework that does not require calibration, and provides predictions based only on the geometry of the array and the incident flow velocity.

This framework is developed and validated in this paper. Since validation requires information of C_d and $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$, which is very difficult to obtain experimentally (Chang & Constantinescu, 2015), the framework will be demonstrated through comparison to three dimensional (3-D) DNS for arrays of cylinders. The simulations in themselves offer unique insight into the flow field, since existing 3-D numerical studies have tended to use turbulence-closure schemes (Chang & Constantinescu, 2015; Chang et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2019). The present work differs from these earlier studies in that it focuses on high-resolution 3-D DNS of different arrays of a large numbers of cylinders.

2. Predictive Models for the Flow Through a Porous Array

2.1. Modeling the External Flow: Actuator Disc Theory

Actuator disc theory can be used to model depth-averaged steady flow through a disc in a channel of width W (Garrett & Cummins, 2007). The theory assumes that the fluid is incompressible and inviscid, with flow through the disc controlled by the resistance of the array and the channel wall blockage ratio $B = D/W$. Increases in B confine the flow field, inhibiting flow diversion and enhancing mean flow through the disc.

Resolving the through-disc velocity $\alpha_2 U_\infty$ requires application of continuity, energy and momentum conservation to different parts of the external flow field. Applying continuity between the two bounding streamlines in Figure 1c leads to

$$U_\infty D_1 = \alpha_2 U_\infty D = \alpha_4 U_\infty D_4, \quad (3)$$

where D_1 , D and D_4 are defined in Figure 1c. Continuity across the channel between S_1 and S_4 also gives

$$U_\infty \frac{D}{B} = \alpha_4 U_\infty D_4 + \beta_4 U_\infty \left(\frac{D}{B} - D_4 \right). \quad (4)$$

Combining Equations 3 and 4 therefore yields

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{\alpha_4(1 - \beta_4)}{B(\alpha_4 - \beta_4)}. \quad (5)$$

Next, the Bernoulli equation can be applied between the bounding streamlines in both the regions downstream and upstream of the disc:

$$p_1 + \rho \frac{U_\infty^2}{2} = p_2 + \rho \frac{(\alpha_2 U_\infty)^2}{2}, \quad (6)$$

$$p_3 + \rho \frac{(\alpha_2 U_\infty)^2}{2} = p_4 + \rho \frac{(\alpha_4 U_\infty)^2}{2}, \quad (7)$$

where p_i is the pressure at the corresponding sections S_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$). Application of the Bernoulli equation between S_1 and S_4 in the diverted flow also gives

$$p_1 + \rho \frac{U_\infty^2}{2} = p_4 + \rho \frac{(\beta_4 U_\infty)^2}{2}. \quad (8)$$

Combining Equations 6, 7, and 8 yields

$$p_2 - p_3 = \frac{1}{2} \rho U_\infty^2 (\beta_4^2 - \alpha_4^2). \quad (9)$$

Finally, momentum conservation across the channel between S_1 and S_4 can be written as

$$(p_1 - p_4) \frac{D}{B} - F = \left(\rho \alpha_4 U_\infty \frac{\alpha_2 D}{\alpha_4} \right) \alpha_4 U_\infty + \rho \beta_4 U_\infty \left(\frac{D}{B} - \frac{\alpha_2 D}{\alpha_4} \right) \beta_4 U_\infty - \left(\rho U_\infty \frac{D}{B} \right) U_\infty. \quad (10)$$

where the drag force per unit depth F is assumed to have a quadratic dependence on the local velocity. For a circular array, this bulk force can be written as

$$F = \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{C_{da}}{(1 - \phi)} (\alpha_2 U_\infty)^2 \frac{\pi}{4} D^2 = \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{\pi}{4} \Gamma_D D (\alpha_2 U_\infty)^2, \quad (11)$$

where $\pi/4D^2$ is the area of a circular array. F is also equal to the change in streamwise pressure across the disc multiplied by the disc diameter (i.e., $F = (p_2 - p_3)D$), such that combining Equations 9 and 11 gives

$$\frac{\pi}{4} \Gamma_D \alpha_2^2 = (\beta_4^2 - \alpha_4^2). \quad (12)$$

Combining Equations 8, 10, and 12, and simplifying with use of Equation 5, eventually leads to

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{(1 + \alpha_4)}{(1 + B) + \sqrt{(1 - B)^2 + B(1 - 1/\alpha_4)^2}}. \quad (13)$$

Equations 5, 12, and 13 now provide relationships that link the mean flow $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$, that is, $\alpha_2 U_\infty$, to the resistance. For given values of B and Γ_D , these equations can be solved simultaneously for α_2 , α_4 and β_4 . Note that in the limit Γ_D

→ 0 it follows from Equation 12 that $\alpha_4 \rightarrow \beta_4 \rightarrow 1$ noting that $\alpha_4 \leq 1$ and $\beta_4 \geq 1$. Hence, $\alpha_2 \rightarrow 1$ according to Equation 13, which is consistent with undisturbed flow for $\Gamma_D \rightarrow 0$.

2.2. Modeling the Internal Flow: Element-Scale Drag Models

There are three main methods for evaluating the drag coefficient C_d : (i) direct measurement of C_d in numerical simulations, for which the C_d value is estimated through Equation 2 with the drag force output from Nektar ++; (ii) assuming $C_d = 1$ and (iii) adopting an empirical model. An example of (iii) is that in Tanino and Nepf (2008), which was developed for an infinitely wide array with random arrangement, and is expressed as

$$C_d = 2 \left(\frac{\gamma_0}{Re} + \gamma_1 \right), \quad (14)$$

in which, γ_0 increases from 25 ± 12 at $\phi = 0.091$ to 84 ± 14 at $\phi = 0.15$ (a value it retains up to $\phi = 0.35$), and $\gamma_1 = (0.46 \pm 0.11) + (3.8 \pm 0.5)\phi$. The first and second terms in right-hand side of Equation 14 describe the contributions from the viscous force and form drag on the cylinders, respectively. This model indicates that C_d increases with ϕ and decreasing Re . This, in turn, suggests that C_d will increase with Γ_D (increasing ϕ and decreasing Re).

3. Numerical Approach

3-D DNS have been conducted by solving the continuity equation and the incompressible Navier–Stokes (N-S) equations:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}, \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = (u, v, w)$ is the velocity vector, and t is the time. The governing equations were solved with open-source code Nektar++ using the quasi-3D approach (Cantwell et al., 2015). Whilst the flow in the x - y plane was solved using the spectral/ hp element method (Karniadakis & Sherwin, 2005), the spanwise (z) direction was resolved using a Fourier discretization (Karniadakis, 1990). Hence refinement of the 2-D mesh in x - y plane and the number of Fourier modes in the z -direction is required (Cantwell et al., 2015). All the velocities from 3-D simulations in the results section (§ 4) are post-processed on a spanwise-average flow field.

Fifth-order Lagrange polynomials are used on Gauss–Lobatto–Legendre quadrature points with a second-order time integration method and a velocity correction scheme in the Galerkin formula (Karniadakis et al., 1991; Vos et al., 2011). A circular computational domain of radius $20D$ was adopted for the x - y plane with the cylinder array was placed at the center of this domain, that is, $(x, y) = (0, 0)$. The mesh included 48 cells around each cylinder surface, and the radial thickness of the cell next to each cylinder surface was $0.03 d$. The cell expansion ratio was kept below 1.2 in the whole domain. The spanwise length of 1–2D with a number of Fourier modes in the range of 64–256 was employed to ensure adequate resolution of element-scale and array-scale 3-D flow structures.

A Dirichlet condition was specified for velocity on the inlet (i.e., $u = U_\infty$ and $v = 0$ on the front half of the circumference of the computational domain), while a Neumann velocity boundary was used for velocity on the outlet boundary (i.e., $\partial u / \partial n = 0$ and $\partial v / \partial n = 0$, on the back half circumference, where \mathbf{n} is the normal vector to this boundary). While a no-slip boundary condition was enforced on all cylinder walls, a slip-boundary condition was applied on both bottom and top boundaries of the domain. The time step was chosen as $0.002d/U_\infty$.

Due to high computational cost for each 3-D simulation, 2-D simulations were used to complement to the 3-D simulations. The 2-D simulations employed the same boundary conditions and x - y mesh as in the 3-D simulations. For a 2-D simulation, the computational cost ranged from approximately 3,000 to 60,000 core hr for arrays with N of 7–109. For a 3-D simulation, 0.18 billion computational mesh cells were used for $N = 109$, with 3.8 M core hours required for the full simulation to $10,000t^*$ ($=tU_\infty/d$).

Figure 2. (a) Configuration of a circular array of cylinders with different numbers of elements. Dashed lines represent circumferences of arrays; (b) a square array in staggered configuration; (c) a circular array in random configuration; (d) Summary of characteristics of arrays shown in panels (a–c).

To explore the validity of this framework for different array arrangements and shapes, a square array with a staggered arrangement (Figure 2b) and a circular array with a random configuration (Figure 2c) were also simulated. Relative orientation between cylinders is shown in Figures 2a–2c. The array dimensions and density of each configuration are given in Figure 2d. The Reynolds number ($=U_\infty d/\nu$) was 200 for all simulations.

4. Results

4.1. Flow Characteristics at the Array-Scale

Figure 3 illustrates how the instantaneous and temporally averaged flows vary with Γ_D in the 3-D simulations. The instantaneous flow is visualized by the spanwise vorticity $\omega_z = (\partial v/\partial x - \partial u/\partial y)$. At low Γ_D ($=0.6$, Figure 3a), vortices shed from individual cylinders dominate the flow field and the velocity between adjacent rows of cylinders within the array approaches the ambient velocity ($\bar{u}/U_\infty \sim 1$; Figure 3c). The element-scale vortices are dissipated rapidly downstream (see Figure 3a). The contour plot of streamwise velocity (and the streamline spacing) illustrates that the flow passing through the array and the flow diverted around the array are close to laterally uniform.

At large $\Gamma_D = 697.3$, array-scale vortex shedding occurs immediately behind the array (Figure 3d). The flow external to the array is characterized by four regions: a low-velocity region both upstream and downstream of the array, and two high-velocity regions on either side of the array (Figure 3h). The streamlines expand significantly upstream of the array, then diverge around and through the array, and eventually converge downstream of it. Strong flow diversion coincides with very low velocity within the array (Figure 3h). The convergence of streamlines is associated with wake mixing induced by the array-scale vortex structures (Figure 3d).

Figure 3. The variation of (a–d) the instantaneous (visualized by spanwise vorticity at $z/D = 0$) and (e–h) temporally-averaged flow fields with Γ_D in 3-D simulations.

At intermediate $\Gamma_D = 3.4, 8.2$ (Figures 3b and 3c), element-scale flow structures from different rows of cylinders interact with each other, causing strong element-scale wake interactions. With increases in Γ_D , the dominant vortex structures in the system change from the element scale to the array scale, and flow divergence increases, with less flow passing through the array.

Whilst the general flow field in Figure 3 is similar to that assumed in actuator disc theory, the turbulence associated with element-scale and array-scale vortices (Figures 3a–3d) in the wakes of the array is not considered in the theory. The influence of turbulence on the accuracy of the theory has been studied in Nishino and Willden (2012) by altering β , which quantifies the ratio of energy converted to turbulence to the energy removed (by drag) from the mean flow. It was found in Nishino and Willden (2012) that actuator disc theory underestimates the mean flow with increasing β , but only by 2% for $\beta = 0.1$ and $B = 0.036$. Here the turbulent kinetic energy in the wake has been integrated over the full water depth and a plan area covering $y/D = [-1, 1]$ and $x/D = [-0.5, S_4]$ where S_4 is the location where the two bounding streamlines behind the array become parallel. For all the cases considered here, $B = 0.025$ and β is less than 0.1 such that the turbulence is expected to have secondary influence on the theory prediction. This expectation is borne out in Section 4.3 when the theory is quantitatively compared with the simulations.

Figures 3e–3h also reveals a smooth transition in the transverse direction from the large diverted flow velocity to the smaller wake flow velocity behind the array, which is different to the step change from $\alpha_4 U_\infty$ to $\beta_4 U_\infty$ assumed in actuator disc theory. As outlined in § 2.1, the diverted and wake velocities enter the energy and momentum balances as squared quantities. Consequently, errors associated with an assumption of uniform flow can be quantified by comparing the square of the spatially averaged streamwise velocity to the spatial average of

Figure 4. (a) Mapping mean flow (at black contour lines) out on the field of streamwise velocity for the array with $N = 109$ and $\Gamma_D = 6.9$; (d, e) comparison between segment-averaged velocities $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_x$, $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_y$ (markers) and mean flow $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ (lines) for $N = 31$. The segment-average velocities $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_x$, $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_y$ are evaluated within each segment bounded by adjacent dashed lines in panels (b, c), respectively.

the square of the streamwise velocity at S_4 in 3-D DNS. Differences in these two results are small in both the diverted and wake flows, with RMS differences of $<1\%$ for all the cases. This suggests the assumption of a uniform velocity profile in the diverted and wake flow does not significantly compromise the theory.

4.2. Flow Characteristics at the Element Scale

The mean streamwise velocity within the array is shown in Figure 4a for a circular array with $N = 109$. It is seen that the contour lines form a loop encompassing each cylinder, and the loop size increases with x/D . These loops separate the lower-velocity regions around individual elements from the higher-velocity regions in the gaps between elements.

Segment-averaged streamwise velocities ($\langle \bar{u} \rangle_x$, $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_y$) (defined in Figures 4b and 4c) are used to characterize the local distribution of flow in both the streamwise and transverse directions within the array. The scale of the averaging volume is chosen to be large enough to filter out the velocity heterogeneity associated with individual cylinders but sufficiently small to provide high-resolution estimates of the velocity distribution over the array.

Figure 4d shows that the measured $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_x$ is close to laterally uniform across the full range of $\Gamma_D = 0.6$ –697.3. There is also good agreement between $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ and $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_x$, with normalized RMS errors 1.8%, 3.5%, 3.7% and 3.8% for the four cases in descending order of Γ_D . The agreement suggests that the mean flow is representative of $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_x$ at each

Figure 5. Comparison of measured and predicted mean flows in 3-D and 2-D simulations.

transverse location where the cylinders are situated. In contrast, $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_y$ linearly decreases, across the line of $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ at $x/D \approx 0$ (see Figure 4c). The RMS errors between $\langle \bar{u} \rangle_y$ at $x/D = 0$ and $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ are 2.8%, 8.6%, 13.2% and 6.7% for the four cases, respectively.

4.3. Prediction of Mean Flow

The predictive framework for mean flow based on integration of actuator disc theory with element-scale drag models is demonstrated in this section. Implementing the first two drag models introduced in Section 2.2 (i.e., direct measurement of C_d , and $C_d = 1$) is straightforward, whilst for the empirical model of Equation 14 an iterative solution is required because of the dependence of C_d on Re . This solution is implemented by using U_∞ to initially estimate C_d (hence Γ_D). $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ computed with this Γ_D is then used to update C_d iteratively until C_d and $\langle \bar{u} \rangle$ are matched in the solution.

The performance and applicable range of the predictive framework depends on which drag model is used to estimate C_d (Figure 5). Direct measurement of C_d in Γ_D yields the best predictions of the measured $\langle \bar{u} \rangle / U_\infty$ across the full range of $\Gamma_D = (0.1-1,000)$ (with a normalized RMS error of 1.9%, Figure 5a). Predicting C_d through Equation 14 allows model performance that is reasonably accurate (RMS error 3.9%, Figure 5b). Modeling simply with $C_d = 1$ (Figure 5c) as adopted by Creed et al. (2017) provides good prediction of $\langle \bar{u} \rangle / U_\infty$ when $\Gamma_D < 1$ but increasingly overpredicts $\langle \bar{u} \rangle / U_\infty$ with increasing Γ_D . This overprediction is due to stronger element-scale wake interaction (see Figure 3), and the increase of C_d (as described in Section 2.2) with Γ_D .

Figure 5 demonstrates that the predictive framework is applicable for different arrangements (staggered, concentric, random) and shapes (circular, square) of the array. The arrays in Figure 5 have array-to-element diameter ratios $D/d = 3.6-180$ and the total number of cylinders $N = 7-109$. The agreement between the 2-D and 3-D results in Figure 5 suggests that the 2-D simulation is adequate to resolve the relation between $\langle \bar{u} \rangle / U_\infty$ and Γ_D across the parameter space considered here.

The universal agreement in Figure 5 provides validation for the assumption of scale separation. At the array-scale, the flow diversion external to the array is controlled by the bulk resistance, regardless of element-scale internal flow within the array and the array geometry. Likewise, at the element-scale, the flow within the array behaves similarly to that in an infinite array, independent of the complex external flow.

It is informative to consider some limitations of the present work. Firstly, since the influence of bed friction is neglected, the results here are more applicable to low wake stability number (defined in Chen & Jirka, 1995). It would require alterations to the array- and element-scale models for shallower flows, characterized by high stability number. Secondly, the framework only predicts the spatially averaged velocity in the array. A multiple-streamtube approach (Draper et al., 2016; Paraschivoiu, 1988) could be investigated to extend standard actuator disc theory to account for spatial variability in mean flow. Thirdly, the framework has been applied to fully emergent rigid cylinders with constant frontal area. If an array is submerged the framework could still be adopted,

but the performance will depend on how accurately C_d can be estimated by drag models of emergent cylinders. Fourthly, whilst this framework is demonstrated to be applicable to compact arrays, extending the framework to other geometries, such as arrays with streamwise length greater than width, requires further work. Finally, for large non-uniform arrays it may be worthwhile exploring alterations to the framework if more than two scales emerge (e.g., large meadows comprised of patches of vegetation (Bastyan & Cambridge, 2008) and tidal turbine farms (Cooke et al., 2016)).

5. Conclusions

This study combines theory and DNS to investigate flow through a circular array of cylinders in a steady current. Based on analytical and numerical results, we have used an idea of scale separation to integrate array-scale actuator disc theory and element-scale drag models to develop a predictive framework for the mean flow through the array across the full practical range of Γ_D . Two key findings underpin the development of this framework. Firstly, an array in the range of $\Gamma_D < 1,000$ can be mathematically represented by a single laterally uniform bulk force such that actuator disc theory can be used to model the flow external to the array. Secondly, the average drag coefficient of the array elements can be predicted by element-scale drag models of an infinitely wide array and even an isolated cylinder. This framework is validated through comparison to novel high-fidelity DNS for arrays with 7–109 cylinders, array-to-element diameter ratios 3.6–181 and different arrangements (staggered, concentric, random) and shapes (circular, square) in both 2-D and 3-D flows. Applying this framework only requires knowledge of the array geometry and incident flow.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in creating the figures of this paper are available at Zenodo (He et al., 2023) under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Acknowledgments

The first author would like to acknowledge the support from the Australian Government and the University of Western Australia by providing RTP and UPA scholarships for a doctoral degree. This work was supported by resources provided by the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre with funding from the Australian Government and the Government of Western Australia. Open access publishing facilitated by The University of Western Australia, as part of the Wiley - The University of Western Australia agreement via the Council of Australian University Librarians.

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